

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF USING INTERACTIVE METHODS IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS

Muminov Isroil Xudoyshukur ugli

Master's degree student of Denov Institute of Entrepreneurship and Pedagogy

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Abstract. *This article talks about the content and essence of interactive methods that serve students to gain more meaningful knowledge and help organize teachers' classes in an interesting way, and the stages of their application in primary education classes.*

Keywords: *interactive method, primary education, "Cluster", method, stage, method, innovative lesson, organization.*

In the **introduction** of the article, modern information technologies create wide opportunities in the use of interactive methods. Interactive methods and didactic games, which are part of them, increase the quality and efficiency of education and serve to train competitive personnel. The effectiveness of these interactive methods largely depends on the correct organization of the innovative activities carried out in the educational institution. The use of interactive methods greatly helps to increase the effectiveness of the lesson. The specific features of interactive education are as follows: conducting informal debates, free presentation of educational material, a small number of lectures, but a large number of seminars, creating opportunities for students to take initiative. , consists of methods such as giving tasks for working as a small group, large group, sing team, doing written work, which are of special importance in increasing the effectiveness of educational work.

As we consider on **the theoretical** aspects of the article, the following are listed as pedagogical conditions for the organization of the processes of using interactive methods in the educational institution: formation of the scientific research potential of the educational institution; development of a set of theoretical and pedagogical rules reflecting the specific features of interactive methods; the main conditions for ensuring the organization of the process of using interactive methods are separate aspects of management, that is, the formation of an updated management structure aimed at the organization of this activity.

Also, innovative methods of teaching are widely used in the modern education process. The use of innovative methods of teaching leads to the achievement of expected results in the teaching process. It is appropriate to choose the interactive methods used in the process of innovative education based on the didactic task of each lesson. It should not be forgotten that, while preserving the traditional form of the lesson, enriching it with various methods that activate the activity of learners, will lead to an increase in the level of mastery of learners.

Modern pedagogical technologies guaranteeing the effectiveness of the educational process are widely used in the modern education process in a number of developed countries. The methods of large-scale experiments in the application of these innovative pedagogical technologies are called interactive methods. Interactive educational methods are currently the most common methods and are widely used in all aspects of the educational process. In addition, there are many types of interactive educational methods, which are used in almost all areas of the educational process and are suitable for achieving the intended goals. In practice, it is possible to select from them the ones suitable for the expected purposes and use only the ones relevant to this purpose.

This situation has created the problem of choosing the right interactive educational methods to achieve certain goals. For this, the lesson process should be rationally organized on the basis of a carefully developed plan in advance by the teacher, the teacher should increase the interest of the students and constantly encourage their activity in the educational process, into small pieces, using methods such as problem situation, brainstorming, discussion, guided text, project, working in small groups, role-playing, guided text and students it is necessary to encourage independent performance of practical exercises.

In the **practical** part of the article, the choice of interactive methods in the process of education depends on the educational goal, the number of students and their capabilities, as well as the educational and material conditions of the educational institution, the duration of the teaching system, the pedagogical skills of the teacher, etc. is taken into account. The interactive method is to solve an activity or problem in a mutual dialogue, in the course of thinking in a mutual debate, together. The advantage of this method is that the entire activity teaches the student to think independently and prepares him for an independent life. Interactive methods mean methods that activate learners and encourage them to think independently, with the learner at the center of the educational process. When these methods are used, the teacher invites the learner to actively participate. The learner is involved throughout the process. The benefits of a learner-centered approach include:

- study-learning with higher educational efficiency;
- high motivation of the learner;
- consideration of previously acquired knowledge;
- adaptation of the educational process to the goals and needs of the learner;
- support of the learner's initiative and responsibility;
- the learner learns through practical implementation of acquired knowledge;
- creation of conditions for two-way feedback.

Thus, the use of interactive methods in the process of teaching subjects has its own characteristics. Careful study and practical application of each interactive method used in educational practice expands the thinking of students and has a positive effect on finding the right solution to the problem. It increases the creativity and activity of students. When various theoretical and practical problems are analyzed through interactive methods, the expansion and deepening of students' knowledge, skills, and abilities is achieved.

Indicators such as the extreme importance of innovative innovations in the training of competitive specialists, the fact that the effectiveness and efficiency of socio-economic activity are closely related to innovative activity, and that it is one of the main levers for ensuring the effective integration of education, science and production are in education. shows the importance of innovative management. Therefore, innovative educational technologies are complex integrative systems, which are an organized set of operations and actions aimed at the acquisition of professional skills and personal qualities by students, assimilation of knowledge, determined by the purpose of education. includes z.

When learning interactive methods in education, it is impossible not to dwell on modern electronic tools. They can be called strategic elements of educational innovation. In general education, the interdisciplinary model of teaching is typical, in which subjects have more than necessary information. Using modern information and communication technologies, it is extremely easy and convenient to find and apply information used in the educational process. The

strategy of teaching through interactive methods envisages organizing the educational process in such a way that, as before, the pedagogue is the leading element, only his attitude towards school teachers and himself will change.

Teaching through interactive methods is a modern form of teaching in institutions. The purpose of these methods is to increase the interest of teachers in their subject by using innovative methods of information technology to increase the effectiveness of the lesson, to educate their creative approach to learning subjects; teaching independent work with literature; It is carried out in the way of solving the tasks of demonstrating the use of connections between disciplines. A number of problems are being solved on the basis of this method, named modern educational technologies. New computer information technologies such as moving pictures, teleconference, transliteration, e-book serve to activate the educational process. The educational system based on interactive methods is important not only in learning science, but also in technology. When learning technology, it is recommended to use this educational technology in the following order: setting a technical task by the pedagogue for mastering the subject material by teachers; implementation of ways to solve the technical task by them. In this, teachers write down problematic questions and their scientific assumptions and make an interactive communication plan. This interactive method is based on the mutual activity of the training participants. The lesson began to be organized. The use of innovative methods to improve the effectiveness of primary school classes is one of the forms of independent education. Its effectiveness largely depends on the result of communication between the pedagogue and them.

Therefore, interactive methods are of great importance. Opinions about the results of research on modern educational technologies in various classes, introducing students to the exemplary lives and activities of scientists, teaching them to solve today's pressing life issues at a professional level, and teaching them about science. It is important to increase interest in this way.

Cluster method

One of the active methods is the "Cluster" method. Clustering is a pedagogical strategy that helps teachers think freely and openly about a topic. This method develops multi-variant thinking, the skills of making connections between the studied concepts (events, events). The word cluster means a group.

The cluster method is considered a form of thinking that is not directed to a specific object. Its use is carried out in connection with the principle of human brain activity. This method serves to ensure that the activity of thinking will be in harmony until a specific topic is mastered deeply and thoroughly by future teachers. This method, developed in accordance with the idea of style, is a well-thought-out strategy that can be used in the course of training organized individually or in groups with undergraduate teachers. In group training, this method is manifested in the form of a set of ideas expressed by group members. This creates an opportunity to harmonize the ideas put forward by each member of the group and to find connections between them. Use the cluster method as follows: Write down what you think. Don't think about the quality of your thoughts, just write them down. Do not pay attention to the spelling or other aspects of your writing. Don't stop writing until the allotted time is up. If you can't think of an idea for a certain period of time, then start drawing a picture of something on paper.

Continue this process until a new idea is born. Try to put forward as many new ideas as possible within the framework of a certain concept and show the interrelationship and connection

between these ideas. Do not limit the quality of the set of ideas and show the connections between them. This method can be applied to training as follows:

Organization of the lesson: In order to achieve the effectiveness of mastering a new topic, short repetition exercises will be conducted on the topics covered. It can be organized as follows: By repeating the previous topic, the ground is prepared for mastering a new topic in the minds of teachers. This ensures the effectiveness of mastering a new subject. Based on the cluster method, in the classes organized on a group basis, this method is manifested in the form of a set of ideas expressed by the group members. Each group member puts forward an idea, after which all ideas are combined.

This method improves the independent and free thinking skills of primary school teachers and develops their creative observation potential. At the end of the training, the pedagogue brings their ideas to a certain conclusion and announces them. Their knowledge is evaluated, active participants are encouraged. Homework: It is known that the training of undergraduate teachers is a serious matter. For this, they are required to have knowledge, skills, self-sacrifice, to have their own opinion, to be able to find clear solutions to problems. The cluster method, which is one of the active methods, is important in training teachers who can meet such requirements. This active method of education can be used in training future teachers in all educational institutions. It should be noted that interactive methods are called collective thinking, that is, they are methods of pedagogical influence and are a component of the educational content. The uniqueness of these methods is that they are implemented only through the joint activity of pedagogues and bachelor teachers.

The use of the "cluster" method in the first lesson allows to divide the students into small groups, to determine the level of the students' knowledge of elementary science. Therefore, the main goal of the interactive method is to create an environment for active, free thinking of the student by creating the most favorable situation for the learning process. There are many methods of modern educational technologies. These methods can be used depending on the student's age, psychological characteristics, and level of knowledge. In elementary grades, "brainstorming", "work in small groups", "test", "role games", "cluster", "scene" lessons, "game", "mind wheel", "title text from me from you" game, "presentation and discussion", "finish the sentence", "Creative work" work methods with a goal in mind, creating a problem, preparing students to work in this process, and having certain skills expected results can be obtained if it is used in such cases.

1. Game, conversation, argument, meeting, husband that each lesson, in the family, in the public place, in the neighborhood, is focused on the education of moral concepts with the clarity, historicity and modernity of the goal.

2. Organization of the educational session using various methods: audio, video, presentation, visualization, live speech.

3. Teachers should have new technological skills and creativity.

One of the most popular types of modern educational technologies today is interactive methods. Interactive methods are a joint activity of the student and the teacher, and mainly encourage students to think.

The essence of interactive methods used by teachers in primary classes, the design of the educational process, preliminary diagnosis of the level of knowledge, skills and qualifications of primary education teachers, the educational activities organized by them controlling the content, evaluating their knowledge, skills and qualifications has a positive effect on the assimilation of

theoretical knowledge to determine the effectiveness of pedagogical activity. Also, recognition of the formation of the skills of successfully organizing communication with teachers, primary education teachers, creative approach to pedagogical activities, ability to evaluate pedagogical situations and organize behavior and actions in accordance with them. will be done.

In **conclusion**, it should be said that by teaching using interactive methods for elementary school students, the interest of the growing younger generation in learning will increase, and they will learn more about the information that needs to be learned. can express his personal opinion. In classes organized on the basis of interactive methods, students learn to work in groups and students learn to respect each other.

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